

MECHANICAL SUPPORT OF BLOOD CIRCULATION

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Annotation. Attempts to strengthen the insufficient pumping function of the heart by mechanical intervention have been made since the early 1960s, when Spyridon Moulopoulos and his co-authors first created a revolutionary intraaortic balloon pump (IABP).

Various auxiliary ventricular systems (ventricular assistdevice; VAD) have been developed. The most commonly used type in modern practice involves the use of a pump with a continuous flow that enhances the ejection from the LV (LVAD – left ventricular auxiliary circulation apparatus) (RV). Less often, such devices are used to enhance the function of the right or both ventricles. There are implantable and percutaneous models of them. In a relatively small INT rEPID study, a statistically significant benefit from the use of such devices was demonstrated to reduce the incidence of complications and mortality in patients who could not be prescribed transplantation, but LVAD was established (compared with the data of patients who received only drug treatment) [6]. The latest generation of VADs are percutaneous devices that use impeller pumps that provide axial flow, as opposed to the centrifugal flow used in traditional implantable LVADs.

Keys words: cardiogenic shock, treatment, therapy, occurrence.

In comparison with IABP, these latest percutaneous models (for example, Tandem Heart and Impella) improved hemodynamic parameters, but did not affect the level of mortality [1]. Extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) combines the action of a peristaltic pump, a heat exchanger and an oxygenator, the action of which is aimed at supporting the functions of the cardiovascular and respiratory system. There are venous and veno arterial forms of ECMO. The former provide support only for the respiratory function, the latter are a substitute for the cardiopulmonary complex. ECMO is used for various pathologies, including cardiogenic shock, acute respiratory distress syndrome and cardiac arrest.

There is evidence that ECMO can positively affect the levels of short- and long-term survival of patients when compared with the data obtained during the use of traditional cardiopulmonary resuscitation in cardiac arrest during hospital stay (especially in patients with primary cardiac pathology) [2, 3]. At the moment, clinicians are increasingly interested in when ECMO should be used in groups of patients admitted to emergency departments. It is hoped that this will significantly improve important neurological outcomes [1]. Nevertheless, at the moment there are no data from randomized studies evaluating the use of ECMO in cardiogenic shock and acute MI, and therefore the benefits of its administration to patients who have not been diagnosed with circulatory arrest have not been evaluated [5] to neglect standard methods of ACS treatment, including the appointment of aspirin and heparin. Patients in a state of cardiogenic shock should undergo an immediate examination to identify the need for revascularization, PCI or coronary artery bypass grafting. The positive effect of revascularization is the higher the earlier it begins. The maximum benefit is achieved in the first 12 hours of its appointment after the appearance of symptoms.

The patient may need to correct hypovolemia by replenishing fluid deficiency, but care should be taken not to provoke or increase pulmonary edema.

In the group of patients who require the appointment of drugs that increase blood pressure, norepinephrine with the addition of dobutamine or milrinone should be considered the drug of choice. Pressor preparations should be used with caution and titration should be performed before administration for the maximum possible dose reduction.

Patients who, despite the use of medicinal substances that increase blood pressure and optimize the water-electrolyte balance, may be candidates for mechanical enhancement of heart function, including the installation of IABP and LVAD.

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